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Content Analysis of Microstructure of Oxford English Sindhi-Dictionary 2010

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Abstract :The aim of this research was to critically analyze the microstructure of the oxford English Sindhi dictionary (2010). In order to achieve the aim of the study, an objective was set to find out the way information was presented in the microstructure of OESD (2010) which was the sample of the study. Afterwards, the study was designed qualitatively as per the nature of the study and it was decided after going through a huge corpora related to critical dictionary analysis. The dictionary was analyzed through content analysis. This required a sample to be selected and taken from every twentieth page of the dictionary. The results of the study were discussed descriptively. The results of the study showed that there was a lot of information present in the microstructure of the dictionary. This information was related to meaning, labels including word class, symbols, abbreviations etc. It also included pronunciation of words. First of all meaning was present at lexical level and in the form of definitions. Secondly, the word class of the entries was also given in front of them. Moreover, abbreviations and acronyms were also present in the microstructure but these were not differentiated from each other. Most importantly, certain phonemes were presented in a wrong way. That is to say the symbols which were given for the sounds did not represent the actual sounds of the given words. This was found to be one of the mistakes which might have taught the learners wrong pronunciation of the words.

Keywords: lexicography, microstructure, dictionary, critical dictionary analysis, OESD (2010).

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1.1 INTRODUCTION

In ESL/EFL countries like Pakistan where language is learned through the set of rules and tools provided to them like, Grammar books and Dictionaries, bi-lingual dictionaries, there it is considered as reliable source of vocabulary building and most helpful tool. Bilingual dictionaries are bi-directional they go from one direction i.e. from English to Another language. Bilingual

dictionaries provide equivalent of source language in target language. EFL/ ESL Readers are left with only two choices to understand the meaning of text they are dealing with, by using dictionaries or going through context. The efficient readers prefer the use of dictionaries despite of going through the context. “It is estimated that vocabulary learning from context is only possible and reliable when the student understands between 95% and 98% of the text” (Laufer 2005).

Dictionary is considered a well set and well-arranged list of lexemes that the speakers of a language use in their context of interaction. It helps a learner practically and according to Dash.N.S (2005) language learners consult it to gain information related to a lexeme. This information includes meaning, origin, usage and pronunciation of that particular word.

Additionally, Zgusta (1971) provides that a dictionary is a systemized list of lexemes. It is arranged based on the social uses of those lexical items in a particular context of their use. These lexical items are mainly compiled by lexicographers from the way these are used by speech communities. These are arranged separately so that the learner may come to know about them easily through a dictionary.

1.2 Structure of Dictionary

The structure mainly shows the components of a dictionary. It also represents the way a dictionary is designed: it shows its whole structure. Three terms are usually used to describe the structure of a dictionary as per Meta lexicography. These terms are: Mega-structure, Macro-structure and Micro-structure.

Fig:1.1 Structure of Dictionaries

1.3 Synchronic & Diachronic development of English Sindhi Dictionaries

Historical and synchronic are defined by Pearsall.j (2015). Synchronic study of a dictionary is defined as the study which is done at a particular time. Contrastingly, the diachronic dictionary approach is related to the study of language throughout time.

Shah Zulfiqar and Soomro Ashfaque (2016). Since the early period of British rule over Sindh, a good work has been done in dictionary making in Sindhi in order to make the native people familiar with English language. Two massive works appeared in this period i.e. English-Sindhi and Sindhi-English dictionaries. In 1849, the English-Sindhi Dictionary published from Bombay was compiled by Captain George Stack, a Deputy Collector of Hyderabad and the was edited by Sir Barrow Ellis in the year 1855. The script used in the compilation of both of these dictionaries was Devnagri. an English man Mr. Shirt and two Sindhi scholars M/s. Udha Ram Thanwardas and Mirza Sadiq Ali Beg conjointly compiled Sindhi-English Dictionary (1879)- the first immense work in bilingual dictionary in Sindhi lexicography. The script the dictionary published in was Arabic-Sindhi script and this was first in this script as prior to this dictionary, no other dictionary was published in Arabic-Sindhi script.

If we trace the Sindhi lexicographic work before and after the creation of Pakistan. There are two significant dictionaries compiled before Pakistan, Permanand Mewaram's English-Sindhi Dictionary (1933) and an other was by Anandram T. Shahani (1939). Many Lexicographers put a lot of their efforts into this field. Some of them are as: Abdul Na Pirzado (2007), Abdul Rashid Memon (2007), Bashir Mangi (2006), Abdul Hussain Memon (1959), Ghulam Mustafa Shah(1972), Ali Dino Shah.

After the independence, the first two are held among the pioneers of the English-Sindhi Bilingual lexicography. Furthermore, online and paper dictionaries are compiled and published by Sindhica Academy, Oxford university press Karachi and Sindhi Language Authority Hyderabad Sindh Pakistan.

1.4 Research Question

The current study will be followed by these two important questions.

1. How the information contained in microstructure is presented in OESD (2010)?

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

A research was conducted in the field of Lexicography in 2015 by Mgr.Zuzana Cechova the research analyze the micro structure of English language dictionaries, Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary, Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary and The Co build English for Learners Dictionary. 11 groups of words have been selected to analyze: Abstract, concrete, countable and uncountable//// nouns, adjectives derived from verbs, adverbs, irregular verbs, words that differ in English and American pronunciation. The findings of study reveals that the OALD is very precise in the definition and divides the senses according to slight differences in meaning, in comparison with the CALD or the Co build Dictionary. The definitions in the CALD are more general and they give more senses which are introduced separately in the OALD. Regarding the pronunciation researcher finds that all the three dictionaries provide difference in American and British pronunciation. Co build dictionary has no stress markers in the transcription of pronunciation resultantly this brings ambiguity for nonnative speakers of English. After analyzing above mentioned dictionaries researcher recommended Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary as helpful for learners.

Another research was done in 2016 (Shah.Z and Soomro.A). The researcher selected eight (08) bilingual English to Sindhi dictionaries listed below:

English and Sindi Dictionary, by Lakshuman Vishnu Parajpye (1868),

English-Sindhi Dictionary, by Nanikram D. Mirchnadani (1928),

English-Sindhi Dictionary, by Dulamal Bulchand (1928),

A New English–Sindhi Dictionary By: Permanand Mewaram (1933),

English to Sindhi Dictionary, by Anandram T. Shahani (1939-41),

Sindhica: English to Sindhi Dictionary (2003),

Advanced Dictionary: English to English and Sindhi, by Abdul Nabi Pirzada,

Oxford English-Sindhi Dictionary (2010).

Method of investigation is content analysis. The paper provides general overview of meaning and pronunciation presented in English to Sindhi dictionaries. Researcher explores that all the dictionaries included in study provide good deal of meaning but most of the dictionaries lack pronunciation, grammatical information and usage.

Similar research was conducted on presenting pronunciation in English to Sindhi bilingual dictionary in 2015 by (Shah.Z and Mashori.G). This research studied all the six dictionaries that include pronunciation in them. It was a diachronic study pronunciation based dictionaries. It included the following dictionaries:

English Sindhi Dictionary by Anandram T. Shahani (1939)

Yadgar Dictionary Shah, A. D & Mangi, B. A (1988)

Sindhica English-Sindhi published by Sindhica Academy, Karachi (2003).

Kifayat's English to English and Sindhi Dictionary by Rashid Ahmed Memon (2004).

Advanced Dictionary: English to English and Sindhi by Abdul Nabi Pirzado (2007)

Oxford English to Sindhi dictionary by Shah. Q & Abro. B (2010)

Content analysis is employed as research method. The Researchers have concluded that only Shahni has used the diacritic marks to help the learners to master pronunciation. According to them such usage of the diacritic marks has made it effective in learning English pronunciation. Moreover, other five dictionaries are full of blunders and do not provide accurate pronunciation. Oxford English-Sindhi dictionary use software to read the IPA pronunciation in which translation is converted automatically in pronunciation. It may be software problem which commits mistakes in pronunciation. Furthermore researcher has concluded that there isn't any English to Sindhi dictionary which provides authentic pronunciation.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This study is mainly qualitative in nature. In critical dictionary research the researcher had employed content analysis to accomplish the set goals. It was because, according to Cohen, Manion,; & Morrison, (2009), Scott (2006) and Julien (2008) content analysis as a method of qualitative research is mainly used for textual investigation.

In Content analysis a text is closely and critically analyzed by examining what it contains. Julien (2008) provides that different instances may be provided by the identified categories of the data. Through this analysis one can ensure whether certain elements are present in the provided document. After the classification of the categories, the researcher made an attempt to ensure whether the data is categorically comprehensive and well defined (Julien, 2008). The researcher through this analysis tried to confirm the covered components in the microstructure of the selected dictionary. Furthermore, the researcher confirmed how the pronunciation is presented through

IPA. Additionally, the meaning equivalents were also checked, by checking the way it was presented in the dictionary..

4.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The data presented in this section is taken from the oxford English Sindhi dictionary 2010. This section provides a clear picture of the data related to the findings. In short, it provides the reader with the knowledge related to the way dictionary was analyzed and the findings which emerged after its analysis. It also includes in it discussions which shall clarify the terms, figures and tables which are given in certain sections.

This research is related to the way entries are presented in the dictionary. The researcher analyzed the way the identified information is presented in the dictionary. The analysis related to these entries has been discussed in this section. Moreover, there is a separate heading related to the representation of pronunciation of head words. The pronunciation, which has been done in IPA, of English words has been compared with its equivalent which is in OALD 9th ed. the analysis has been given in this following sub-sections.

4.1 Meaning

Presenting meaning in a bilingual dictionary is most important part of the dictionary making. A compiler has to deal with two different languages. There are two types of meaning presentation in bilingual dictionary by providing lexical equivalent and other is giving definitions (shah 2012). The dictionary under the study presents both lexical/ one word equivalent and definitions. Additionally, connotations and polysemous meanings are also provided in dictionary. Some examples which the researcher found during analysis are given below:

a Lexical equivalent

Table 4.1: Lexical Equivalent, From Oxford English Sindhi Dictionary 2010.

Page No.	Word	Meaning
144	Ballot Paper	ووٽ جي پرچي
1082	Mechanic	مشين جو مستري
1156	Naturally	فطري طور
1642	Sip	ڍڪ

b Definitions

Table 4.2: Definitions From Oxford English Sindhi Dictionary 2010.

Page No.	Word	Definition
105	Augustan	رومي شهنشاه آگستس يا سندس دور متعلق خاص ڪري لاطيني ادب جي سونهري دور طور
584	Episcope	غير شفاف شين کي ظاهر ڪري ڏيکاريندڙ
22	Adivasi	هندستان جو اصلوڪو قبيلو
1802	Taoism	تاؤمت خاڪساري ۽ پاڪبازيءَ جي تلقين جي لکت تي پڌل چيني فلسفو تي لاٽوز (500 ق م)

Discussion

Meaning in this dictionary is presented as clear as possible both denotatively as well as connotatively. As far as the examples related to denotative meaning are concerned, some of them have been quoted above. Moreover, similar entries can be found eg: Vase گلدان page no: 1973, Stoep وړانڊو 1736, comparable P.345, mom ما اما . Secondly, connotative meanings are also provided for example lion P.1020 بهادر شخص، دلير، سورهي. Additionally, similar kind of words can be found beast P.142. The compiler has presented meaning in one or two words. Moreover, definition method has also been employed for words which cannot be explained in one word. Some of the examples related to such entries are given above. Other examples related to this entry can be found: Drachm P.522, Ergative P. 587, Hedonism P.813, Leopard P.1003 . If one turns towards the definitions provided in dictionary, these definitions are precise and authentic. Other than the above discussed entries that have only one of these like certain entries have only denotative meaning, certain have only connotative meaning. But, despite these, there were certain entries that had connotative meaning, denotative meaning, idiomatic usages and their use in different linguistic contexts. In this case there was an entry e.g. Heart which have three connotations and 25 idioms , see Break on page number 203 , burn page number 224, Go. page number 746 to 748 are translated in Sindhi throughout the dictionary. These meanings are numbered separately to facilitate and to overcome the ambiguity for learner. That numbering represents meaning of a word. For example if a word has three meaning then each meaning has been written with a number. The drawback of

c Usage

The usage of the words in the dictionary is given in brackets which are given below the meaning of an entry. It follows examples related to the usage of that head-word. Moreover, in the usage section, it had also been discussed whether the word is being used transitively or intransitively. It also includes the structural formation of a sentence in which the head word is used eg. وغيره
in, out: Bounced into the room: تيزيءَ سان ڪمري ۾ گهٽي پيو , ڪان اڳ Into + verbal noun:
Bounced him into signing: زور بار وجهي هن کان صحيح ورتي وئي . This structural formation also tells the learner about the neighboring structures, including its colloquial, which are used with the word, for example whether a word follows a ‘that clause’ or not. In addition, the varietal differences of the word, that is to say its usage, in its different varieties of English, is also given in the dictionary, for example Pinole P.1319 : اسم اميرڪ . As far the functional use of the entry is concerned, the dictionary also teaches a learner the way a word is used in different ways like informal, formal, slang etc. In simple words the dictionary provides information related to the use of a head word in different registers. For instance. P. 77 Appeal: in Law ڪنهن ڪيس جي اڪلاءَ لاءِ اعليٰ عدالت
ڪنهن رجوع. In addition to the above points, the geographical location, on the basis of a word’s usage, has also been given in the entries. It means like in what places the word is being used. Such usage refers to the linguistic map of the world.

d Usage notes

✓ **refute** / rɪ'fju:t / v.tr. رِفِيُوت / فمت: 1- (بيان يا ان جي جاري
ڪندڙ جي) ترديد ڪرڻ، ڪوڙو ثابت ڪرڻ. 2- دليل دلائل سان رد ڪرڻ، غلط ثابت
ڪرڻ. 3- تڪراري: (دليلن کان سواءِ) نه مڃڻ يا رد ڏيڻ ○ **refutable** □ صفت:
قابل ترديد. **refutation** / rɛfju'teɪʃ(ə)n/ اسم. **refuter** اسم.

■ استعمال: ڪي ماڻهو *refute* جي مفهوم 3 ۾ استعمال ڪي غلط سمجهن ٿا،
انهي معنيٰ ۾ ان تي *repudiate* جو شڪ ٿئي ٿو.

Figure 4.1: Image from Oxford English Sindhi Dictionary 2010 (Usage Note)

Discussion

In addition to the above given labels, an additional point in an entry is of usage notes. This is different from the usage which has already been discussed above. These usage notes are given in parenthesis in an entry where-ever necessary. The usage notes provide the learner the information related to the use of a word in a particular context or domain. The usage notes are not similar to its definitions. The usage notes restrict the definition of a word to a certain domain. The domains of usage vary word to word, as it is quite clear that a word might belong to a standard variety or a non-standard variety of a language.

e SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

This dictionary contains symbols and abbreviations as separate entries. The symbols are mostly related to scientific fields like chemistry, physics, mathematics e.g: p.1047 M3: وڏو Mega, p: 1039: Lu- عنصر Lutetium ڪيميا , p: 544 E- بنياد اٽڪل جي برابر as far as abbreviations are concerned, they are related to medical, social, academic, scientific, organization related, food, news agency, tools, ranks and some of them are related to different professions as well e.g: EVA: Extra vehicular Activity: هوا بازي م , BCG: Bacillus calmete Guerin: سله جي بيماري جا . حفاظتي ٽڪا . It was also found during the analysis that there were certain abbreviated forms in English that do not have their meaning equivalents, definitions or explanations in Sindhi language. Most importantly, the OESD has used their system of abbreviations; a very considerable defect is acronyms are also labeled as abbreviations e.g. UNICEF, NEPRA. Whereas, acronyms are the words that are formed with the initials of words that makeup name of something (OALD 9th ed.)

4.3 Pronunciation

As discussed earlier the pronunciation in the dictionary was found to be having problems in it. That can be defined in a way that the given phonemes do not represent the actual sounds of certain word. The extracted data related to such finding has been given below in the table.

Table 4.3.1: Pronunciation. Comparison of examples from Oxford English Sindhi Dictionary 2010 and Oxford Advanced learners dictionary.

Word	Pronunciation in Sindhi	IPA transcription given Oxford English Sindhi Dictionary 2010	transcription given in OALD 9 th Edition
Admiral	آیدمرل	/ 'adm(ə)r(ə)l /	/ 'ædmərəl /
Bank	بیگ	/ 'baŋk /	/ 'bæŋk /
Practice	پریکٹس	/ 'praktɪ(ə)s /	/ 'præktɪs /
Tactic	ٹیکٹک	/ 'taktɪk /	/ 'tæktɪk /

Instead of using monophthong open mid front/æ/ in the words like bank, the dictionary provides monophthong open front /a/.

Table 4.3.2. Pronunciation. Examples from Oxford English Sindhi Dictionary 2010 and Oxford Advanced learners dictionary.

The SEnglish monophthong open mid central long /ɜ:/ for the sound occurring in the words like

Word	Pronunciation in Sindhi	IPA transcription given Oxford English Sindhi Dictionary 2010	transcription given in OALD 9 th Edition
Bird	No pronunciation	/ bə:d /	/ bɜ:d /
Girl	گ	/ gɜ:l /	/ gɜ:l /
Whirl	وَل	/wɜ:l /	/ wɜ:l /
Pearl	پل	/ pɜ:l /	/ pɜ:l /

‘Bird’ and ‘Whril’ is wrongly given as close mid central/ə:/ (ə- this symbol is known as schwa in IPA and this is the shortest and the most frequently used vowel in English language and this sound replaces many long and short vowels in connected speech).

Table 4.3.3. Pronunciation. Examples from Oxford English Sindhi Dictionary 2010 and Oxford Advanced learners dictionary.

Word	Pronunciation in Sindhi	IPA transcription given Oxford English Sindhi Dictionary 2010	transcription given in OALD 9 th Edition
Pair	پيئي	/ pɛ: /	/ peə(r) /
Dare	ڊيئي	/ we: /	/ deə(r) /
Where	ويئي	/ we: /	/ weə(r) /
Wear	ويئي	/ we: /	/ weə(r) /

English monophthong open-mid front /ɛ:/ is used instead of diphthong/ eə/ in words like ‘Wear’ and ‘Pair’.

Table 4.3.4. Pronunciation. Examples from Oxford English Sindhi Dictionary 2010 and Oxford Advanced learners dictionary.

Word	Pronunciation in Sindhi	IPA transcription given Oxford English Sindhi Dictionary 2010	transcription given in OALD 9 th Edition
Height	هائت	/ hʌɪt /	/ hait /
Fight	فائت	/ fʌɪt /	/ fait /
Bride	برايد	/ brʌɪd /	/ brait /
Tight	تائت	/ tʌɪt /	/ tait /

Diphthong /ʌ ɪ/ is used instead of /aɪ/ as in Tight and Fight.

Table 4.3.5. Pronunciation. Examples from Oxford English Sindhi Dictionary 2010 and Oxford Advanced learners dictionary.

Word	Pronunciation in Sindhi	IPA transcription given Oxford English Sindhi Dictionary 2010	transcription given in OALD 9 th Edition
Fire	فَائِي	/ 'fʌɪə /	/ 'faɪə(r) /
Liar	لَائِي	/ 'lʌɪə /	/ 'laɪə(r) /
Dire	دَائِي	/ 'dʌɪə /	/ 'daɪə(r) /
Buyer	بَائِي	/ 'bʌɪə /	/ 'baɪə(r) /

Triphthong / ʌɪə/ is used instead of /aɪə/ like in ‘Dire’ and ‘liar’

Discussion

During the analysis related to the presentation of pronunciation in the dictionary, the researcher found that the transcription of certain words was not given correctly. This transcription, as discussed in the preface section of ‘Oxford English-Sindhi dictionary’, has been done with the help of unnamed software. The developers have just mentioned that they had done the analysis with the help of computer programming, which could be the reason that the transcription of the words has not been represented accurately in the dictionary. There are clear mistakes in the symbolic representation of phonemes related to an entry. That is to say the actual pronunciation of the words was different whereas their transcription was presented inaccurately. This particular finding of mispronunciation was also found by Shah.ZA and Mashori .G (2015). Another finding in this connection was related to the presentation of English pronunciation in Sindhi orthography. It was found that the pronunciation of the words in Sindhi could not match the actual pronunciation of English words. That is to say, English and Sindhi versions of the pronunciation of a single entry did not match each other.

5.0 CONCLUSION

The findings of the research are related to oxford English Sindhi Dictionary OESD2010. The dictionary was analyzed through content analysis. The results of the data show that meaning was

presented very well but there was problem that the polysemous meanings were paraphrased. Similarly, symbols and abbreviations were also present in it but the problem was that all abbreviations as well as acronyms were not distinctively mentioned. There no clear boundary which could differentiate an acronym from an abbreviation.

Additionally, word classes were also mentioned in the dictionary. And, the dictionary is all well versed when it comes to the contexts of the usage of words. Finally, the pronunciation part was also found to be having errors which can also be called as misrepresentation of phonemes. In broader terms these phonemes were monophthongs, diphthongs and trip thongs.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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